

The Impact of Explicit Convection on User-Relevant Projections of Rainfall Extremes Over Africa

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Abstract:

Future changes in rainfall extremes, wet or dry, are critical for today's decision-makers, who require robust knowledge of model uncertainties. It is well-known that in most locations wet extremes will become more intense, but little is known about the robustness of their magnitude of increase. We show substantial spatial and seasonal variability in these changes, and that this variability differs significantly between a convection-permitting model (CPM) and a parameterised model (ParM) over a pan-Africa domain. We focus on all-value percentiles (*not* wet-value percentiles) which are more user-relevant, being inversely proportional to return period. We then begin to work towards an understanding of these geographic variations in the magnitude of change. These variations, and particularly their difference between the CPM and ParM, appear to be determined more by their different storm dynamics than by changes in large-scale thermodynamics. Further elaboration has not yet been straightforward, but we add to evidence that rainfall-ascent-moisture coupling in extreme storms is stronger in the CPM than ParM, and speculate that this model difference may play an important role in their different projected change in behaviour. We also assess the magnitude of projected changes in dry spell frequency, showing that this too has high heterogeneity, dependent on location, season and duration, and also differs substantially between the CPM and ParM. This study adds evidence to the concept that it is worthwhile using CPM projection data to adjust CMIP projections of rainfall extremes, and with further work this research will also aid evaluation of the defensibility (or otherwise) of both CPMs and ParMs.

1. Introduction:

- Future changes in rainfall extremes, wet or dry, are critical for today's decision-makers.
- Usable risk-based projections require robust understanding and knowledge of modelling uncertainties, both their range and the possibility of systematic bias.
- We know that in most locations and seasons, wet extremes will become more intense. However, this knowledge is insufficient for decision-makers. The magnitude of increase is also critical.
- Similarly, we know that the frequency and duration of dry spells is projected to increase in most locations and seasons, but again more research is required to provide robust local estimates of plausible ranges of magnitude for these changes.
- Studies show that convection-permitting models (CPMs) usually provide more reliable distributions of rainfall intensity than parameterised models (ParMs), with consequential impacts on large-scale climate change, and likely also on teleconnections.
- However, CPMs are expensive, so simulations are usually relatively short timeslices, with poor sampling of modelling uncertainties. They are also restricted to typically continental-sized domains, so do not yet incorporate global-scale interactions from an improved representation of convection.
- On the other hand, the cheaper ParMs better sample modelling uncertainty, are able to represent global-scale interactions, and include the effects (and data) associated with long-term transient change. In some circumstances (metric, location, timescale) their projected change may be almost as robust as that of CPMs, although this point of view is often not adequately emphasised.
- So CPM projections must be combined with those of ParM ensembles such as CMIP6 and CORDEX. Development of such distillation methods requires understanding of the robustness of both CPMs and ParMs. And for statistical methods, such as Mittal et al. (2021), it is helpful to know the locations, seasons and metrics for which the CPM-based adjustment factor is both substantial (*i.e.* worthwhile) and defensible.
- To date, few studies have focussed on understanding geographic variations in the magnitude of the projected change in rainfall extremes, and crucially their differences in this regard between CPMs and ParMs, and hence the defensibility of each. Yet these variations are important for users.
- For user relevance, an important detail is also hidden in the calculation of percentiles for wet extremes. Several previous studies have focussed on wet-value percentiles, *e.g.* the 99th percentile of rainfall amounts that fall during wet 3-hour periods, excluding times when rainfall is below a dry value threshold. This may be helpful for physical understanding. However, users are interested in return periods, which equates to all-value percentiles, computed using all 3-hour periods. Wet-value percentiles are strongly influenced by changes in the number of dry days, whereas all-value percentiles are not. So in the context of flooding for example, a wet-value percentile would exaggerate the larger increase in wet extremes found in CPMs (*c.f.* ParMs) because CPMs also tend to have a larger increase in the frequency of dry values.
- We necessarily focus on short return periods due to the short length of the CPM simulations (10 years), due in turn to computational limitations; our favoured 99.9th percentile of all 3-hourly data equates to a return period of 1.4 years for 90-day seasons. Longer return periods can instead be addressed through statistical techniques, such as extreme value theory or machine-learning, although these require assumptions about the shape of fit or power of the training model, respectively, leading to associated sensitivities in conclusions.

This study therefore aims to further examine and understand the projected local change in user-relevant metrics of wet and dry extremes. We focus on geographic variations in the magnitude of these changes, which are critical to users, and the differences between a CPM and ParM, both run over a pan-Africa domain. Process-based understanding of these spatial patterns also provides an additional route towards deeper understanding of the reliability – and hence usability – of CPMs and ParMs.

What follows is an interim report on progress towards these aims prior to retirement of the lead author. It is written in note form for time efficiency, with apologies to readers who find this style disconcerting.

2. Data

a. Model Experiments

- 10-year control ('Ctl'; 1997-2007) and future ('Fut'; *circa* 2100) time-slice simulations, using the CP4A and P25A models run with a pan-Africa domain (CP4A = convection-permitting model at 4.5km resolution for Africa, P25A = parameterised model at 25km resolution for Africa).
- Described by Stratton et al. (2018), Kendon et al. (2019), Senior et al. (2021).

b. Data Processing

- Precipitation data (P) is accumulated over 3-hour periods, total column water vapour (TCW), near-surface (1.5m) air temperature ($T_{1.5}$), near-surface dew point temperature ($T_{d,1.5}$) and near-surface relative humidity ($RH_{1.5}$) are sampled hourly and then averaged over 3-hour periods (except Fig.9), mid-tropospheric descent (ω at 500hPa; ω_{500}) is sampled every 3 hours, and dry days (DD) is the total number of days in the simulation with rainfall less than 1 mm/day.
- Data for one missing file, 07:00 on 21 June 2003 for CP4A Ctl, was filled with 07:00 data from the previous day.
- Future–Control anomalies are computed by subtraction, with the exception of P and TCW variables which are computed as Fut/Ctl ratios (unless otherwise stated) because for these zero-bounded fields their subtractive anomalies often simply reflect their climatologies.
- It is important that the same spatial scale of rainfall events is considered for both models, so (except where otherwise stated) the CP4A 3-hourly data is regridded to the P25A grid prior to further data processing.
- As per sect.1, percentiles are computed from data at all time points. So for analyses over all months, we use 8/day x 30 days x 12 months x 10 years = 28,800 data at each location, and so for seasonal analyses 7,200 data. We focus on the 99.9th percentile of rainfall ($P^{99.9}$; lower percentiles correspond to even shorter return periods, and exhibit smaller climate responses and model sensitivity).
- Seasonal means are computed for the four standard seasons: MAM, JJA, SON, DJF.
- Only sub-Saharan Africa is analysed, south of 20°N.
- Arid regions are excluded because wet extremes and dry spells are less relevant and likely governed by different processes, so all analyses (maps and spatial medians) are masked to omit locations where the annual or seasonal (as appropriate) CP4A climatology is less than 1mm/day (the CP4A climatology is also applied to P25A data for consistency).

3. Future Change in the Probability Distribution of Rainfall Intensity, and Model Sensitivity

Fig.1:

- The CP4A Ctl climate has more dry 3-hr periods than P25A.
- The CP4A Ctl climate has more intense wet events (*e.g.* 1 in 1000 3-hr periods) than P25A.
- In the future, dry 3-hour periods remain dry in both models (ratio =1), but this result extends to higher percentiles in CP4A.
- Light rainfall events usually become dry in the future in CP4A (median is zero for mid-range percentiles), and usually become even lighter in P25A.
- The wettest 3-hours typically become more intense in the future, with median increases in $P^{99.9}$ of 39% in CP4A and 33% in P25A.
- Note that, although we analyse projection anomalies in percentile space, one might consider mm/day values on the x-axis to be more user-relevant. However, the advantage of computing percentiles is that they remove the effects of differential bias in Ctl climate between CPM and ParM, which can easily be bias-corrected. A percentile-based analysis is also relevant for Q-Q mapping that can be used to synthesise different evidence lines (*c.f.* Mittal et al. 2021).

In summary, as is well-known, the projected future change is to a climate with less frequent but more intense rainfall in both models. However, increases in the intensity of wet extremes are inevitably less for all-value percentiles than for wet-value percentiles, with the former being more relevant due to their inverse proportionality to decreases in return period.

Recommendations for further analysis:

- Add wet-value percentile plots for direct comparison with all-value percentile plots.
- Add analysis of CP4A on its native (4.5km) grid.

4. Spatial Pattern of the Change in Wet Extremes, and Model Sensitivity

How does the change in magnitude of wet extremes vary geographically, and how does this differ between the CPM and ParM?

Figs.2,3:

- Again we see that the intensity of high rainfall extremes is larger in the future climate, *i.e.* $\Delta P^{99.9} > 1$, with exceptions in only a very few locations (Figs.2,3).
- Again, there's a tendency for this increase to be a bit smaller in the ParM than the CPM (Fig.2, and centre-of-gravity in Fig.3), but there is also a significant minority of locations where the increase is actually larger in the ParM than CPM (Fig.3).
- The magnitude of $P^{99.9}$ increase exhibits substantial spatial and seasonal variability in both models (Fig.2).
- But the large-scale patterns of change often differ between the models (Figs.2,3).
- The ParM pattern of change is more heterogeneous than the CPM (Figs.2,3).
- P25A exhibits a larger range of Fut/Ctl ratios than CP4A (Fig.3), and $\Delta P25A > \Delta CP4A$ is more common in regions of large $\Delta P^{99.9}$.
- Both models exhibit a lot of small-scale spatial noise, suggesting (not surprisingly) sampling issues due to the short simulation length (Figs.2,3).
- Nevertheless, some large-scale similarity exists between the CP4A and P25A patterns of $\Delta P^{99.9}$, as well as many differences (at the 2° grid scale they have 36% common variance).

Figs.2,3 compared $\Delta P^{99.9}$ for 3-hourly rainfall at identical spatial scales (~25km) for the CPM and ParM. To achieve this, the CPM data was first smoothed across several grid-lengths, whereas the ParM data was analysed on its native grid so retaining the effects of numerical noise. Does this make a difference to the magnitude and pattern of change in the CPM?

Fig.4:

- This pattern of CP4A change is very similar to that of Fig.2, *i.e.* results are broadly insensitive to whether the 3-hourly CPM data is analysed on its native grid or smoothed to the P25A grid.
- However, the median change in intensity of wet extremes is lower for rainfall data on the CPM native grid. We speculate that a physical threshold may sometimes be reached in the CPM Ctl on its native grid that cannot be (much) exceeded in Fut, whereas these exceptional extremes are removed by the spatial smoothing applied to the upper panels of Fig.2.

Are these local differences between the CPM and ParM change in the intensity of wet extremes statistically significant? Unless otherwise stated, analysis of both models hereafter reverts to using 3-hourly rainfall at the same 25km spatial scale.

Fig.5:

- The substantial small-scale spatial heterogeneity in the upper panels reiterates the sampling issues in these short simulations.
- But areas of large-scale coherence are also clearly apparent, where either $\Delta P^{99.9}$ is generally larger in CP4A than P25A (more prevalent; plotted values > 1), or some regions where $\Delta P^{99.9}$ is generally larger in P25A (plotted values < 1).
- The lower panels assess the statistical significance of these model differences, using a Bootstrap test to assess the null hypothesis that the ratio of ratios is unity (*i.e.* the projection anomalies of two models' underlying populations are locally identical).
- ~30% of unmasked points are significant at the 10% level, so these model differences in $\Delta P^{99.9}$ are clearly field significant.
- Regions of larger $\Delta P^{99.9}$ in both the CPM and ParM are statistically significant.

In summary, the large-scale pattern of the projected increase in intensity of wet extremes (and shortening of return periods) differs significantly depending on whether convection is parameterised or explicit. Usually $\Delta P^{99.9}$ is larger in CP4A (as is well-known), but some coherent region-seasons of larger $\Delta P^{99.9}$ are also found in P25A. For purposes of distilling projection data across disparate modelling approaches, these results add evidence to the idea that it is worthwhile using CPM projection data to adjust CMIP projections of wet extremes (*i.e.* such adjustments notably affect outcomes), although of course this is predicated on the assumption that the local CPM projections are more reliable.

So we now ask what causes this difference in the large-scale patterns of response between the models? Can we find evidence that these patterns are likely physically more robust in CP4A? The remainder of this article seeks to address these questions.

5. Drivers of the Pattern of Change in Wet Extremes, and Model Sensitivity

What drives these regional variations in the impact of convection modelling on projected change in wet extreme return periods? Is it primarily a response of storms to differences in

large-scale climate change, or is it more due to geographic variations in the change in storm dynamics and their sensitivity to large-scale drivers? This section begins to examine this, although a more complete understanding awaits more in-depth research.

a. Large-Scale Drivers

Is the large-scale pattern of $\Delta P^{99.9}$, and its sensitivity to convective representation, driven by the large-scale pattern of change in thermodynamic fields? And likewise, the difference between the two models' large-scale pattern of $\Delta P^{99.9}$?

Fig.6:

- The pattern of projected change in the intensity of CP4A wet extremes is only weakly related to the large-scale pattern of change in near-surface dew point temperature.
- This is primarily through changes in near-surface relative humidity (and similarly total column water vapour), rather than temperature.
- Perhaps a weak relationship with the pattern of change in large-scale ascent is apparent.
- There is little or no relationship with the pattern of change in dry day counts, which may be a crude proxy for the pattern of change in convective inhibition (this should be verified).
- Similar relationships are found in P25A (not shown).

Fig.7:

- Unlike $P^{99.9}$, the pattern of change in these candidate drivers is very similar between the two models, especially for temperature and moisture, *i.e.* their pattern of seasonal mean change is not much affected by the models' representation of convection.
- This suggests that the large-scale pattern of thermodynamic change is not the primary driver of the pattern of change in the intensity of wet extremes and its difference between CP4A and P25A.

Fig.8:

- This confirms that model differences in the patterns of change in the large-scale drivers considered here are not the primary driver of the model difference in the pattern of change in the intensity of wet extremes.

In summary, it appears that spatial differences in the magnitude of the models' pattern of change in wet extremes is determined more by local storm dynamics and its response to large-scale thermodynamic patterns, than by changes in the large-scale thermodynamic patterns themselves. However, this result is also likely partially dependent on the experimental design: the regional CP4A and P25A simulations are driven by identical remote large-scale climate change, so this will tend to lessen the relative role of large-scale thermodynamic change.

Recommendations for further analysis:

- $\Delta P^{99.9}$ and Δs of the above candidate drivers should be smoothed to a 2° scale, and the above analysis repeated to reduce the role of small-scale sampling noise, especially in $\Delta P^{99.9}$.
- More careful consideration should be given to the use of subtractive versus ratio calculations of projection anomalies for each variable.
- Repeat these spatial scatter density plots for smaller areas to assess whether different drivers dominate in different regions.

b. Strength of 'Rainfall – Ascent – Water Vapour' Coupling Within Storms

Jackson et al. (2020) find stronger coupling of rainfall, vertical motion, and TCW in CP4A than P25A. We examine this further.

Fig.9:

- In this sub-section only, hourly rainfall accumulations and TCW are sampled every 3 hours (not accumulated or averaged over 3 hours) to be more consistent with the 3-hourly sampling of ω_{500} . This has a substantial impact on the results; without this change, little differentiation between the CPM and ParM is apparent.
- This analysis reiterates the finding of stronger rainfall-ascent-moisture coupling in CP4A (top row) than P25A (middle row) when compared on the same spatial scale.
- The bottom row shows that this important model difference is only partly because the CP4A 3-hourly data has been spatially smoothed (whereas the P25A data is not smoothed).

In summary, rainfall-ascent-moisture coupling is stronger in the CPM than ParM. Jackson et al. (2020) suggest this stronger coupling more realistic.

Recommendations for further analysis:

- Plot the bottom row for the whole of sub-Saharan Africa.

c. Changes in ω_{500} & TCW Extremes, and their Relationship with Changes in Mean

Does the stronger rainfall-ascent-moisture coupling in CPM storms also affect the association between patterns of change in moisture, vertical motion and rainfall extremes? And do these relate to changes in the climatological means of these variables?

Fig.10:

- In the CPM, the spatial pattern of the projected change in rainfall extremes is much more closely associated with the pattern of extremes of moisture than of vertical motion.
- Whereas in the ParM, the pattern of the projected change in rainfall extremes is more closely associated with the pattern of extremes of vertical motion.

Fig.11:

- Medians (not shown):
 - Rainfall: Larger in Fut than Ctl (medians > 1). Larger increase in extremes than climatology for both models. Somewhat larger increase in extremes in the CPM (39%, *c.f.* 33% in the ParM), slightly smaller increase in climatology in the CPM (13%, *c.f.* 15% in the ParM).
 - TCW: Local values consistently larger in Fut than Ctl (middle row graphic). Similar median climatological change between the CPM and ParM (42%, 43%, respectively). Slightly smaller change in extremes in the CPM (39%, 43%, respectively).
 - ω_{500} : Little projected change in medians, except for a median increase in extreme ascent in the CPM.
- Both models exhibit moderate correlation between their patterns of $\Delta P^{99.9}$ and ΔP_{Clim} (top panels), and also between models for their changes in climatological rainfall (ΔP_{Clim}) (not shown, $r = 0.73$). This suggests that model sensitivity of the pattern of $\Delta P^{99.9}$ is not related to (the lower) sensitivity of their patterns of ΔP_{Clim} .
- The CPM has greater spatial variability in its changes in moisture extremes ($\Delta TCW^{99.9}$) than the ParM.

- Both models exhibit weaker relationships between their patterns of change in vertical motion extremes and its climatology.

In summary, Fig.10 shows that the greater role of moisture coupling in the CPM storms (besides coupling with vertical motion) (*c.f.* Jackson et al. 2020) is also reflected in a greater similarity of large-scale patterns of change in moisture and rainfall extremes, compared with the ParM.

Recommendations for further analysis:

- Results are sensitive to whether anomalies are computed as Fut-Ctl or Fut/Ctl, so this needs more careful consideration as to which is appropriate for each variable and context
- Repeat with data smoothed to a 2° scale
- Reverse Fig.10 axes and add regression lines and gradients
- Plot the distributions of ω_{500} & TCW against percentile, and their Fut anomalies, as Fig.1

d. Differential Sensitivity of Rainfall to Moisture Changes

Jackson et al. (2020, Fig.12) show pan-Africa differences in the rainfall-moisture relationship between the CPM and ParM. We examine this further here, and whether it might contribute to differences in the large-scale pattern of change in wet extremes.

Figs.12:

- Here $\Delta P^{99.9}$ and ΔTCW_{Clim} are computed as subtractive anomalies.
- As expected, projected increases column moisture content are associated with increases in the intensity of wet extremes.
- In some region-seasons, P25A exhibits some exceptionally large increases in $\Delta P^{99.9}$ per unit increase in column water content.
- Some of CP4A's largest increases in $\Delta P^{99.9}$ per unit ΔTCW_{Clim} are over Lake Victoria, *c.f.* Finney et al. (2020)
- In terms of explaining the large-scale pattern of $\Delta P^{99.9}$, it is statistically inevitable that the patterns of $\Delta P^{99.9}/\Delta TCW_{Clim}$ and $\Delta P^{99.9}$ are related, and so it is that pattern correlations are high ($r = 0.84$ and 0.79 for CP4A and P25A, respectively, combining the 4 seasons).

Recommendations for further analysis:

- Plot maps of the regression of ω_{500} against rainfall, TCW against rainfall, and TCW against ω_{500} , for those 3-hourly time points where rainfall exceeds its local 99th percentile. For Ctl and Fut data, then Fut-minus-Ctl regression slopes, and compare analyses of CP4A and P25A data for each.

6. Spatial Pattern of the Future Change in Dry Extremes

Fig.13:

- Dry spells are defined as consecutive dry days (DD) with prescribed minimum duration.
- Dry spells are usually more frequent in the future climate of both types of model (as is well-known).
- The magnitude of this increase has large spatial and seasonal variability, and also depends on dry spell duration.
- In most location-seasons $\Delta CP4A > \Delta P25A$ (as found in other studies), but in some locations $\Delta P25A > \Delta CP4A$.

- Large-scale similarity between the CP4A and P25A patterns is negligible over southern Africa in DJF, with the exception of a weak pattern correlation for the shortest dry spells.

In summary, the magnitude of the projected change in dry spell frequency has high heterogeneity, dependent on location, season and duration, and usually differs substantially between the CPM and ParM.

Recommendations for further analysis:

- Assess maps for the whole of sub-Saharan Africa and all seasons.
- Investigate the drivers of these spatial variations in the magnitude of change, and so also the reasons for their difference between the CPM and ParM.

7. Conclusions

- We further examine the projected local change in user-relevant metrics of wet and dry extremes, focussing on geographic variations in these changes, and their differences between a CPM and ParM. The varying magnitude of future changes in extreme events is critical to users. Understanding this may also improve assessments of the reliability – and hence usability – of both CPMs and ParMs.
- The increase in the intensity of wet extremes is inevitably less for all-value percentiles than wet-value percentiles, with the former being more relevant due to their inverse relationship to changes in return period.
- The large-scale pattern of the projected increase in the intensity of wet extremes (and shortening of return periods) notably differs between the CPM and ParM (36% common variance at the 2° grid scale), with statistical testing easily rejecting a null hypothesis of equivalence. This adds evidence to the idea that it is worthwhile using CPM projection data to adjust CMIP projections of wet extremes (assuming that the local CPM projections are defensibly judged more reliable).
- These spatial differences in the magnitude of the CPM versus ParM pattern of change in wet extremes appear to be determined more by their different storm dynamics and its response to large-scale thermodynamic patterns, rather than by their changes in the large-scale thermodynamic patterns themselves (although this likely depends in part on the experimental design).
- Further analysis has not yet revealed a straightforward explanation of the models' patterns of future change in wet extremes, or their sensitivity to explicit versus parametrised convection. This may or may not be possible using diagnostics across the entirety of sub-Saharan Africa.
- We add to evidence that rainfall-ascent-moisture coupling in extreme storms is stronger in the CPM than ParM, and speculate that this also impacts the models' large-scale patterns of change in wet extremes.
- Projected changes in dry spell frequency also have substantial regional and seasonal variability, as well as duration dependence, and usually differ substantially between the CPM and ParM.

Recommendations for future work:

- Further consider the role that rainfall-ascent-moisture coupling plays in extreme storms, their future change, and its impact on the models' different climate change responses.
- If necessary, consider a single sub-region and season as a case-study for further progress, rather than a pan-Africa all-season approach.

- A process-based approach towards understanding the pattern and model sensitivity of changes in dry spell frequency would also be invaluable towards better assessing the reliability of this aspect of CPM and ParM projections. This should include evaluation of the roles of resolution and convection on local scale ‘teleconnections’, land-surface feedbacks, and boundary-layer processes.
- The extent to which the pattern of change in extremes is sensitive to large-scale patterns of thermodynamic change should be further explored using the new Met Office ensemble of CMIP6-driven CPM and ParM projections. (As an aside, note that these are not downscaling experiments as such. The large size of the pan-Africa domain will cause the large-scale behaviour of these simulations to depend as much on the structure and physics of the Met Office RCM as it does on the lateral boundary data of the CMIP GCMs; *c.f.* Rowell and Chadwick [2018]. We argue that the value of these experiments will be to enhance physical understanding of the sensitivity of a range of plausible remote forcings on Africa [as opposed to regional, within-domain, processes], rather than provide users with potentially more reliable estimates of uncertainty.)
- For the objective of improved distillation of CPM and ParM data:
 - Statistical approaches (*c.f.* Mittal et al. 2021) require knowledge of the circumstances, metrics and regions that the CPM projections are sufficiently different to those of a parallel ParM in order to be worthwhile applying (as well as defensibly different). The conceptual model of Rowell and Berthou (2023) could be extended alongside the analysis of sect.4 above to assess this.
 - Continued exploration of – and intercomparison with – other approaches to distillation of projection data is also recommended, such as process-based methods (*e.g.* Klein et al. 2021) (although more resource intensive), and machine-learning techniques.

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Fig.1: Upper panels: Distribution of the spatial median of 3-hour rainfall against all-value percentiles, for CP4A (left) and P25A (right), for Ctl (solid line) and Fut (dashed line). Lower panels: Distribution of the Fut/Ctl ratio of 3-hour rainfall for CP4A (solid line) and P25A (dashed line). Local percentiles are masked for aridity in each season (sect.2b), then spatial and seasonal data is concatenated for each percentile to compute its median. Note, the shortened x-axis range plotted in the upper panels.

CP4A

P25A

Fig.2 Maps of Fut/Ctl 99.9th percentile of 3-hour rainfall ($\Delta P^{99.9}$) for CP4A (upper panels) and P25A (lower panels).

Fig.3 Spatial scatter density (2D histograms) of Fut/Ctl 99.9th percentile of 3-hour rainfall ($\Delta P^{99.9}$) for CP25A against CP4A. Data are seasonal grid-box values for sub-Saharan Africa for the four standard seasons. Fut/Ctl ratios are on the P25A grid (left), or averaged to a 2° grid (right). Frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, and the blue line is at $y=x$.

Fig.4 Maps of Fut/Ctl 99.9th percentile of 3-hour rainfall ($\Delta P^{99.9}$) for CP4A on its native 4.5km grid (then averaged to a 0.25° grid for plotting purposes).

Fig.5 Upper panels: maps of CP4A/P25A ratio of $\Delta P^{99.9}$ in each model. Lower panels: likewise, but ratios smoothed to a 2° grid, and the contour marks where 25% of ratios on the P25A grid are significantly different from unity at the 10% level.

Fig.6 Spatial scatter density (2D histograms) of (top left to bottom right) $\Delta T_{d,1.5}$, $\Delta T_{1.5}$, ΔTCW , $\Delta RH_{1.5}$, $\Delta \omega_{500}$ and ΔDD , each against $\Delta P^{99.9}$. Data are CP4A seasonal grid-box projection anomalies for sub-Saharan Africa (means for y-axis data) for the four standard seasons (except simulation counts for ΔDD). Frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, and the sign convention for ω_{500} is positive downwards.

Fig.7 Spatial scatter density (2D histograms) of P25A against CP4A climatological projection anomalies for (top left to bottom right) $\Delta T_{d,1.5}$, $\Delta T_{1.5}$, $\Delta TCW_{1.5}$, $\Delta RH_{1.5}$, $\Delta \omega_{500}$ and $\Delta DD_{1.5}$. Data are seasonal mean grid-box anomalies for sub-Saharan Africa for the four standard seasons. Frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, the blue line is at $y=x$, and the sign convention for ω_{500} is positive downwards.

Fig.8 Spatial scatter density (2D histograms) of CP4A-P25A differences in (top left to bottom right) $\Delta T_{d,1.5}$, $\Delta T_{1.5}$, ΔTCW , $\Delta RH_{1.5}$, $\Delta \omega_{500}$ and ΔDD , each against the CP4A/P25A difference in $\Delta P^{99.9}$. Data are seasonal grid-box differences between projection anomalies for sub-Saharan Africa (means for y-axis data) for the four standard seasons. Frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, and the sign convention for ω_{500} is positive downwards.

Fig.9 Map of correlations between rainfall and ω_{500} (left), rainfall and TCW (central), TCW and ω_{500} (right), using 3-hourly time points from the Ctl simulation where rainfall exceeds its local 99th percentile. Top row: CP4A using data on the P25A grid. Middle row: P25A using data on its native grid. Bottom row: CP4A using data on its native grid (here for South Africa only due to the complexity of processing this much larger dataset). Input data is sampled every 3 hours over the full annual cycle (prior to selecting extreme wet events), with instantaneous values for TCW and ω_{500} , and rainfall accumulated over the subsequent hour.

Fig.10 Spatial scatter density (2D histograms) of $\Delta TCW^{99.9}$ (upper panels) and $\Delta \omega_{500}^{0.1}$ (lower panels) against $\Delta P^{99.9}$ for CP4A (left panels) and P25A (right panels). Data are seasonal grid-box projection anomalies for sub-Saharan Africa for the four standard seasons. Frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, and the sign convention for ω_{500} is positive downwards.

Fig.11 Spatial scatter density (2D histograms) of the projected change in extremes against the change in climatology (average of all time points), for rainfall (upper), TCW (middle) and ω_{500} (lower), for the CP4A (left) and P25A (right) models. Data are the four standard seasons for sub-Saharan Africa. Frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, the blue line (upper and mid panels) is at $y=x$, and the sign convention for ω_{500} is positive downwards.

CP4A

P25A

Fig.12 Maps of $\Delta P^{99.9} / \Delta TCW_{Clim}$ for CP4A (upper panels) and P25A (lower panels).

Fig.13 Maps of changes (Fut-Ctl) in DJF dry spell count (per year) for CP4A (upper row) and P25A (middle row). And spatial scatter density (lower row) of P25A changes against CP4A changes, where frequency contours are on a logarithmic scale, and the blue line is at $y=x$.